

COMMUNICATIVE INTENT DIVERGENCE OF DISCOURSE MARKERS IN SIMULTANEOUSLY INTERPRETED SPEECH

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The present paper examines the divergence in the communicative intent of discourse markers in simultaneous interpretations from English into Slovene in the European Parliament. Specifically, it explores the factors of the original speaker's delivery rate and emotive intensity, and the effects of these factors on the share of equivalent translations, i.e., the translations of discourse markers with the same communicative intent. Moreover, the paper presents a comprehensive translation type classification tailored specifically to the use of English and Slovene discourse markers in simultaneous interpretation. Our classification is grounded in empirical data containing approximately 47,000 tokens, and covers the encountered discourse marker translation types. The results, based on the corpus TolAnSi, indicate that neither the delivery rate nor the emotive intensity level of the speaker affects the share of equivalent translations significantly.

Keywords: discourse marker, simultaneous interpreting, delivery rate, emotive intensity, translation type classification

1 INTRODUCTION

In communication, we do not rely only on propositional content to convey our message. Non-propositional content, or metadiscourse (Hyland, 2005), plays an equally significant role in communication (Hyland, 2005; Mauranen, 2023), and helps us reveal "our intended meanings and communicative intentions" (Mauranen, 2023, p. 1). As a subgroup of metadiscourse (Aijmer, 1996; Maschler, 2009), discourse markers can structure discourse (Schiffrin, 1987; Redeker, 2006), oil the wheels of communication (Müller, 2005), serve as indicators on how to interpret a message (Schiffrin, 1987; Redeker, 2006), and express our attitude towards others (Andersen, 1998; Maschler, 2009).

One would, therefore, expect discourse markers (DMs) to be indispensable in settings where convincing others of one's argument is pivotal. An example of

such a setting is heated debates in the European Parliament, where each Member of the European Parliament is permitted to speak in their mother tongue due to the European Union's multilingualism policy.

To make use of this privilege, simultaneous interpreters are needed to provide live translations. These translations must be as close to the original as possible, so that the listeners relying on the simultaneous interpretation are able to understand the message, and, if need be, respond accordingly. Nevertheless, simultaneous interpreting is a cognitively demanding task, as the interpreter must provide an accurate translation within a very limited timeframe. With this in mind, one might assume interpreters devote more attention to the propositional content and less to the metadiscourse, including DMs.

Consider the following excerpt of a response in the European Parliament within a debate on the Brexit referendum: *"thank you | so | we have to protect ourselves from these evil Russians who are controlling the internet do we"*¹ (Etheridge, 2019) and its rendition into Slovene: *"hvala lepa | seveda | zaščiliti zavarovati se moramo pred temi zlobnimi Rusi"* (anonymous interpreter) [thank you | of course | we have to safeguard and protect ourselves from these evil Russians]. The DM "so" loses its concluding function, which reflects the speaker's summarisation of previous responses, but gains an affirmative or agreeing function in the translation ("of course"), which is not present in the source language (SL). Conversely, the DM "do we" which serves as a provocation or negative emphasis, is omitted completely in the interpretation. The communicative intent of building on the message of the previous responses, as well as provoking, is consequently lost in the translation.

The present paper examines such divergences in the communicative intent of DMs, and strives to hone in on the factors contributing to them. In particular, we look into how the SL delivery rate and the speaker's emotive intensity affect the simultaneous interpretation of English DMs into Slovene. To guide our investigation, the following research questions have been formulated:

¹ The transcription is divided into segments which are separated by the pipe character. Translations for the Slovene interpretations are provided in square brackets.

- RQ1: Does the SL delivery rate affect the share of the DMs' equivalent translation types?
- RQ2: Does the level of emotive intensity in the SL affect the share of the DMs' equivalent translation types?

2 RELATED WORKS

2.1 Discourse markers

Despite being a popular topic of research, to date, there is no widely accepted definition of DMs (Maschler & Schiffrin, 2015; Fedriani & Sansò, 2017). Instead, consensus is found mostly by listing their properties, which include non-truth conditionality, syntactical detachability (Schourup, 1999; Redeker, 2006), multifunctionality (Schiffrin, 2001), as well as having a metalingual interpretation (Maschler, 2009; Maschler & Schiffrin, 2015). They are one- or multi-word units (Schourup, 1999; Redeker, 2006) encompassing different parts of speech (Schourup, 1999; Fischer, 2006). Similar to Schiffrin's (1987, p. 31) canonical definition of DMs being "sequentially dependent elements which bracket units of talk", Maschler (2009, p. 6) describes them as "metalingual utterances occurring at conversational action boundaries, or frame shifts", whereby frame shifts can be major, such as at the beginning of a new story, or subtle, such as when introducing a side comment.

DMs are generally divided into those pertaining to the ideational or the textual domain, the rhetorical, the interpersonal or the interactional, as well as the structural or the sequential domain (cf. Crible, 2017; Crible & Degand, 2019). These domains are then specified further into thirty functions (Crible, 2017), with which the communicative intent of a DM can be specified further. Maschler (2009), however, includes an additional domain, or "realm", as she terms it, namely, the domain pertaining to the cognitive processes of the participants, which include the functions of realising the need to rephrase one's utterance, information processing, or realising new information. Consequently, she devised a classification of DMs that distinguishes the domain of textual, interpersonal and cognitive DMs. Especially for settings where the cognitive load is very high, such as simultaneous interpreting, the inclusion of the cognitive domain is crucial, as it can hint at possible

explanations of translation choices.

The translation of DMs is, per their definition, a highly complex task (Aijmer & Simon-Vandenberg, 2003), as DMs are characteristically multifunctional. Consequently, they are often omitted in written translations (Aijmer, 2007). This raises the question of how simultaneous interpreters deal with DMs, where the task of providing an accurate translation is even more demanding.

2.2 Simultaneous interpreting of DMs

Simultaneous interpreting is a cognitively taxing task, as the interpreter has to listen to the original speech, translate, utter the translation, and, at the same time, listen to the speaker's next utterance while monitoring one's own output. It is, therefore, a continuous process of listening, comprehending, translating and speaking. At the same time, the interpreter is committed to providing a translation that is as close as possible to the original message. Omitting DMs or changing their meaning would, therefore, breach this principle.

Nevertheless, previous research on the interpretation of DMs has shown that, in legal settings, interpreters systematically omit DMs (Hale, 2004; Blakemore & Gallai, 2014). A study on the simultaneous interpretation of the DM "indeed" into Polish in the European Parliament revealed that the DM is omitted in one-third of the cases, and, when translated, in two-thirds of the cases, the translations are non-equivalent (e.g., generalisations, particularisations, or functional diversions) (Rozumko, 2021). The analysis of the simultaneous interpretation of causal and concessive connective items² in the European Parliament has shown that functionally equivalent translations represent only 40% to 45% of the provided translations (Defrancq et al., 2015).

The above findings provoked the exploration of the causes leading interpreters to omit or change the communicative intent of the DMs functionally.

² In the present study, connective items or connectives (e.g., because, but, so, however) are considered a part of DMs provided they fulfill the requirements of discourse markers as described in Section 3.4.

2.3 Delivery rate

As noted by past research (Defrancq et al., 2015; Rozumko, 2021), the speed at which the speaker delivers the original message (delivery rate) might affect the translation of DMs. Magnifico and Defrancq (2020) found a positive correlation between the factors delivery rate and omissions of connective items, albeit only in the causal and concessive functions. The authors categorised the delivery rate into three groups (below 120 words per minute, 120-159 words per minute, 159 or more words per minute). They found that, beyond the delivery rate of 120 words per minute, the share of the translated connective items starts to drop.

Still, according to general simultaneous interpreting research, a delivery rate of up to 120 words per minute is considered comfortable (Gerver, 1969/2002; Setton & Dawrant, 2016), while, in the past, rates beyond 170 words per minute were considered not possible for simultaneous interpreting (Lederer, 1981). Although simultaneous interpreters have to interpret speeches with a far greater delivery rate than 170 words per minute, current research (Setton and Dawrant, 2016) also notes that, at a delivery rate surpassing 160 words per minute, even the most skilled interpreters are forced to resort to omissions as a coping strategy.

2.4 Emotive intensity

To the knowledge of the author, the link between the emotive intensity of the original speaker, which we define as a combination of non-verbal communication (gestures and facial expressions), paralinguistic phenomena (prosody), verbal behaviour (emotionally charged language), as well as the level of extemporaneity, and translation accuracy of DMs, have not been explored so far.

Nevertheless, the link between emotionally charged language and translation accuracy is documented, and studies show a tendency of simultaneous interpreters in the European Parliament to mitigate their translations (see Kučič & Majhenič, 2018; Beaton-Thome, 2020; Bartłomiejczyk, 2022).

Even though interpreters tend to water down emotionally laden utterances, research into the physiological response of interpreters found that

interpreters are affected by the speaker's emotions (Korpál & Jasielska, 2018). Moreover, interpreters tend to converge emotionally with the original speaker and mimic their physiological arousal, which, as Korpál and Jasielska (2018) presumed, might help to comprehend the communicative intent of the original speaker.

While the two findings of mitigating emotive intensity and emotionally converging with the speaker seem contradictory, they are not irreconcilable. Simultaneous interpreters might well converge emotionally with the speaker and grasp the original communicative intent, yet, for some reason, still opt for a translation divergence.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset

The dataset in this study is part of the corpus TolAnSi and contains 98 speeches by 45 speakers that were simultaneously interpreted by 27 interpreters. The speeches were held in the European Parliament between November 2018 and January 2020 during the Brexit negotiations. They had to be non-read, performed by native English speakers from the United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland, and translated by native Slovene accredited interpreters. The leveraged part of the corpus contains 46,999 tokens and is not publicly accessible yet.

3.2 Annotation procedure

The speeches were transcribed using the transcription tool Transcriber 1.5.1, while the alignment of the source language and the interpretation, as well as the annotation of DMs, was performed using the audio analysis tool Praat 6.3.08. To reduce functional ambiguity during the annotation process, the functional classification of DMs was carried out multimodally, i.e., by viewing the video recordings of the SL speeches in the annotation tool Elan 5.9. All annotations were performed by a linguist.

The transcriptions are separated into segments, corresponding predominately to prosodic units. A trained interpreter aligned the source language segments manually with the corresponding simultaneously interpreted segments.

3.3 Segmentation

As Setton (2011) cautioned, a syntactic-based segmentation is not optimal due to language differences, and could lead to very lengthy segments which are more difficult to align. A prosody-based segmentation, on the other hand, generally results in shorter segments (Setton, 2011). In this light, the Chinese interpreting corpora CECIC (Hu, 2016/2011) and CEIPPC (Wang & Tang, 2020) were segmented according to prosodic units. While pauses are a commonly used delimitator of prosodic units, they are not as useful in simultaneously interpreted speech, as the interpreter often pauses, for example, to ensure that their rendition is accurate (Setton, 2011).

Therefore, in our dataset, a prosodic unit is delimited by a combination of the most commonly used parameters, i.e., pitch reset (Degand & Simon, 2009; Cabedo, 2014; Degand et al., 2014; Zwitter Vitez, 2018; Beňuš, 2021), deceleration or acceleration (Degand & Simon, 2009; Cabedo, 2014; Degand et al., 2014; Zwitter Vitez, 2018; Beňuš, 2021), pauses (Cabedo, 2014; Degand et al., 2014; Zwitter Vitez, 2018; Beňuš, 2021), breathing patterns (inhalations) (Beňuš, 2021), and the presence of DMs (Degand & Simon, 2009; Cabedo, 2014; Degand et al., 2014; Zwitter Vitez, 2018; Beňuš, 2021).

3.4 DM annotation and classification

To identify potential DMs, the candidate items had to have a metalinguistic meaning and be syntactically and semantically detachable. As an optional second-level requirement, the item's multifunctionality and number of potential translation equivalents were considered.

The classification of DMs implemented in this research consolidates Crible's (2017) and Crible and Degand's (2019) with Maschler's (2009) topology. Maschler's (2009) three-pronged topology is used as an overarching categorisation of DMs by categorising DMs as textual, interpersonal, or cognitive. The domains of ideational, sequential, and rhetorical DMs are nested within the textual domain, as they denote semantic relations pertaining to the extralingual world and contain a lower degree of subjectivity. The functions used in the present research are adopted from Crible's (2017) functions, with the addition of cognitive functions and the interpersonal

function of contact maintaining (corresponding to Crible's (2017) monitoring function), which are adopted from Maschler (2009). Due to the specificity of simultaneous interpreting, we added the functions of speech production or planning, as well as hesitation, which Crible and Degand (2019) nested within the sequential domain. Moreover, we followed Crible and Degand's (2019) work in allowing the functions of DMs to cross domains.

Despite this functionally comprehensive and annotationally liberal classification method, as DMs are multifunctional, per definition, a clear-cut functional classification seems inadequate. Therefore, we allowed for multiple functional annotations of DMs in both the SL and the simultaneous interpretations. Doing this, the various functional aspects of a given DM can be captured better, which, in turn, allows for an improved functional translation comparison.

3.5 DM translation classification

To analyse the share of equivalent and non-equivalent translations, translations of DMs were labelled provisionally as equivalents, shifts and omissions. However, the data from the corpus required additional tags, such as when interpreters produce a DM but omit the surrounding segment (tag Missing segment with equivalent), or when the whole segment containing the DM is omitted (tag Missing segment). Additionally, due to the syntactical differences between the languages, we had to account for the criterium of syntactical detachability when deciding on the type of translation provided by the simultaneous interpreter. The translation tags starting with »Non-DM« denote that the DM was translated, but that it does not fulfill the criteria of DMs (as presented in Section 3.4) in the other language.

As a result, translations were divided into two groups – the equivalent translation types:

- Equivalent – a translation with a DM that is functionally equivalent in the target language (see example in Section 4.2.1)
- Non-DM translation – an equivalent translation, but not with a DM, or with an expression that does not qualify as a DM in the target language (see example in Section 4.2.2)

- Close equivalent – a functionally very close translation, but not completely equivalent (see example in Section 4.1.1)
- Non-DM close equivalent – a functionally very close translation, but not completely equivalent, whereby the expression does not qualify as a DM in the target language (see example in Section 4.1.2)

and the non-equivalent translation types:

- Shift – a translation divergence with a DM that does not match the function of the DM in the source language
- Non-DM shift – a functionally different translation with an expression that is not a DM in the target language (see example in Section 1)
- Transformed segment – a non-equivalent translation where the segment is changed completely or a translation with a DM is not possible
- Omission – the DM is omitted in the target language (see example in Section 4.1.3)
- Missing segment – the segment containing the DM in the source language is omitted
- Missing segment with equivalent – the DM is translated, but the pertaining segment is omitted in the target language (see example in Section 4.2.3)

3.6 SL delivery rate classification

The delivery rate of the SL was divided into four rates: low, which designates speeds up to 130 tokens per minute (TPM), moderate, which is up to 160 TPM, high, which is up to 180 TPM, and very high, which is reserved for delivery rates of more than 180 TPM (cf. Monti et al., 2005; Magnifico & Defrancq, 2020).

3.7 SL emotive intensity classification

The following parameters were examined, to determine the level of emotive intensity:

- non-verbal communication, which can be perceived through facial expressions, gestures, posture and physical appearance (e.g., flushed face). The study will look at whether the speaker makes use of them or not, and, if

so, to what degree and how frequently.

- paralinguistic phenomena, i.e., speech prosody – the use of pauses, whether the speaker uses a narrower or a wider pitch/intensity range (which can be perceived as a lively speech), etc.
- verbal communication, i.e., emotionally charged language – the use of provocations, sarcasm, insults, or offensive, vulgar, or politically incorrect expressions.
- the use of speech notes. The study will examine if the speaker uses notes, and, if so, to what degree they rely on them.

The frequency and the degree to which these parameters are deployed by the speakers correspond to the level of emotive intensity, whereby level 1 represents the lowest level of emotive intensity and level 5 the highest level of emotive intensity. Thus, the following levels were implemented:

1 – completely detached, i.e., almost no perceivable non-verbal communication, insignificant speech prosody, relying strongly on notes

2 – calm, but not completely detached (i.e., some perceivable/subtle facial expressions and/or gestures, more varied speech prosody), relying partially on notes

3 – some engagement, i.e., partially lively speech (perceivable through non-verbal communication and paralinguistic phenomena), may contain a mild form of provocation, but without prosodic prominence (raising one's voice or crying), or the use of sarcasm, not relying on notes

4 – lively speech with visible emotions perceivable through paralinguistic phenomena, non-verbal and verbal communication, may include provocation and/or sarcasm, not relying on notes

5 – very lively speech with strong emotions perceivable through paralinguistic phenomena, non-verbal and verbal communication, may include provocation, sarcasm, insults, offensive, vulgar, and/or politically incorrect expressions, not relying on notes.

An example of emotive intensity level 5 is given in Figure 1 (Davies, 2019) which exhibits a negative facial expression, prominent prosody (raised voice),

a »pin-pointing« hand gesture while uttering a vulgar expression (»bollocks to Brexit«).

Figure 1: Emotive intensity 5

3.8 Hypotheses

Building upon the outlined methodology, we posit the following hypotheses:

- H1: Speeches with a delivery rate classified as high and very high have a smaller share of equivalent DM translation types than speeches with a low and moderate delivery rate.
- H2: Speeches with a higher emotive intensity, classified as levels 4 and 5, have a smaller share of equivalent DM translation types than speeches with level 2 or 3 emotive intensity.

4 RESULTS

Overall, 879 DMs were identified in the SL. These 879 DMs correspond to 394 DMs in the target language, irrespective of the translation type. The remaining 485 expressions cannot be classified as DMs, either because they were omitted, or were other expressions that did not fulfill the requirements of discourse markerhood in Section 3.4, in the target language.

The average SL delivery rate was 161.36 TPM and the median was 159.40 TPM, whereby the lowest was 116.81 TPM, and the highest delivery rate was

211.92 TPM. Regarding the categorisation of the speeches into delivery rate categories, only three speeches (3.06%) were categorised as having a low delivery rate, while the majority was represented by the moderate (47.96%) and high (29.59%) categories, leaving approximately a fifth (19.39%) to the very high delivery rate category.

The average value of the emotive intensity was 3.12 and the median was 3.0, whereby no speech was classified with the value 1, and six speeches (6.12%) had the top emotive intensity value 5. The lion's share (42.86%) of speeches had the emotive intensity level 3, and a quarter (25.51%) of the speeches are represented by both the emotive intensity levels 2 and 4.

4.1 SL delivery rate and equivalent translation types

The link between the SL delivery rate and the share of equivalent translation types of DMs is represented in Figure 2, where the bars on the vertical axis represent the SL delivery rates, and the horizontal axis denotes the number of the speeches in each delivery rate group, while the percentages in the stacked bars denote the share of each translation type.

Figure 2: SL delivery rate and translation types

In the following three subsections, examples of the individual translation types will be presented. It must be noted, that the translation type examples chosen for each delivery rate do not indicate that the given translation type is more or less likely to occur in the given delivery rate group. The examples merely serve translation type illustration purposes.

4.1.1 MODERATE DELIVERY RATE

The results show that the moderate delivery rate of 130 to 160 TPM had the greatest share of equivalent translation types, as more than half (53.06%) of the DMs preserved the original communicative intent. The equivalent translation types include the categories Equivalent, Non-DM translation, Non-DM close equivalent, and Close equivalent, which can be illustrated with the example below:

and I hope the next Parliament will address this | secondly sustainable finance should become the norm (Gill, 2019)

in upam da bo naslednji Parlament to rešil | potem trajnostno financiranje naj bo norma (anonymous interpreter)

[and I hope that the next Parliament will solve this | then sustainable financing should be the norm]

The enumerating sequential DM "secondly" is translated with the Slovene DM "potem" [then], a topic resuming or continuing but also enumerating sequential DM. The functions of both DMs are indeed very close, yet an equivalent translation is also possible ("drugič" [secondly]). Therefore, the equivalent translation type cannot be assigned. Such instances were labelled as translation type Close equivalent, which designates a close and completely acceptable, yet not »perfect« equivalent.

4.1.2 HIGH DELIVERY RATE

The second-best results were obtained for the high delivery rate, where 40.79% of the DMs in the category were translated as equivalent types. An illustration of a close translation type with an expression other than a DM is the following case:

a many different organisations and stakeholders have made contact with us throughout our work on this | and I also thank them for their engagement and interest (Palmer, 2019)

imamo veliko organizacij in deležnikov ki so stopili z nami v stik pri delu na tem dosjeju | tako da se tud njim zahvaljujem za angažiranost in interes (anonymous interpreter)

[we have many organisations and stakeholders who contacted us regarding the

work on this dossier | so I also thank them for their engagement and interest]

At a first glance, "and" seems a mere adding sequential marker, but it can also be seen as a concluding rhetorical marker with respect to the previous utterance. Such instances warranted two functional annotations in the SL. In Slovene, the expression "tako da" [so] conveys primarily the communicative intent of conclusion, not as much the sequential addition function. As the translated expression corresponds to at least one of the source DM's functions, an equivalent translation type must be assigned. As the Slovene expression is, in this case, syntactically integrated, it cannot be considered a DM. Consequently, the only fitting translation type is Non-DM close equivalent, designating a functionally close translation, yet with an expression other than a DM.

4.1.3 VERY HIGH AND LOW DELIVERY RATES

The delivery rate categories very high and low had similar results, with the category very high containing 37.18% of equivalent translation types, and the category low containing 36.36% of equivalent translation types. The example below illustrates the translation type Omission that occurred in a speech with a very high SL delivery rate:

well thank you mister President | well I mean there's a big file but ninety percent of the interventions have been on one issue (Dalton, 2019)

hvala | to je velik dosje ampak devetdeset odstotkov komentarjev je bilo v zvezi z enim vprašanjem (anonymous interpreter)

[thank you | this is a big file but ninety percent of the comments pertained to one question]

The three DMs in the SL were all omitted, even though the Slovene equivalents are relatively straightforward ("no" or "ja" [well], and "mislim" [I mean]). The effects of the high delivery can be connected with the interpreter's time lag, since the speaker had already begun to speak while the interpreter was still translating the Chairperson's message.

4.2 Emotive intensity and equivalent translation types

The interplay of the emotive intensity level and the share of equivalent

translation types is represented in Figure 3, where the four bars represent the SL emotive intensity levels, and the horizontal axis the number of speeches in the emotive intensity group, while the percentages in the stacked bars denote the share of each translation type.

In the following three subsections, examples of the individual translation types will be given. Similar to Section 4.1, the examples chosen for each emotive intensity group do not represent the individual group.

4.2.1 HIGH EMOTIVE INTENSITY – LEVEL 5

As per Graph 2, the emotionally most intense speeches (group 5) also exhibited the greatest share, i.e., 67.97%, of equivalent translation types. Such translation types can be illustrated by the next example:

well | this wasn't the plan was it | instead of sunlit uplands the best we are offered is survival (Howarth, 2019)

ja | to ni bil načrt | ali ne | namesto vseh velikih načrtov nam ponujajo preživetje (anonymous interpreter)

[well | this wasn't the plan | was it | instead of great plans we are offered survival]

Both the SL and the interpretation contain the same DMs with the same communicative intent, as "well" and "ja" [right/well] can both signal a negative emphasis at the beginning of the speech. They were classified as negative emphasis interpersonal markers. Likewise, "was it" and "ali ne" [was it] serve the same provocative purpose, and were both classified as monitoring interpersonal DMs. As the functions in both languages overlap, the equivalent

translation type is justified.

4.2.2 LOW EMOTIVE INTENSITY – LEVEL 2

The emotionally least intense speeches (group 2) contained almost half (47.06%) of all equivalent translation types, some of which were suitably translated with expressions other than DMs, as in the following example:

we've now received the latest reports from the platforms | on what they're doing | covering the month of March | a- and we'll publish our assessment of those reports in the coming days (King, 2019)

zdaj beremo najnedavnejša poročila platform za mesec marec | in bomo našo oceno teh poročil objavili v prihodnjih dneh (anonymous interpreter)

[we're now reading the latest reports from the platforms for the month of March | and we'll publish our assessment of these reports in the coming days]

While the expression "in" [and] conveys the same communicative intent, i.e., that of sequential addition, in Slovene, the expression is syntactically integrated. Therefore, it does not meet the criteria for DMs. Consequently, only translation type Non-DM translation applies.

4.2.3 MIDDLE EMOTIVE INTENSITY – LEVELS 3 AND 4

A slightly greater share of non-equivalent translation types can be observed in the groups with the middle emotive intensity values (3 and 4), where equivalent translation types represented 43.32% and 41.83%. The example in the Introduction illustrates a case where the communicative intent diverged, and the corresponding expression was not a DM (translation type Non-DM shift). The case below, on the other hand, demonstrates a translation type where the DM preserves its original communicative intent, but the segment in which it is embedded is omitted (translation type Missing segment with equivalent):

but the problem is this | even though human rights are universal (Daly, 2019)

ampak čeprav so človekove pravice univerzalne (anonymous interpreter)

[but even though human rights are universal]

In the example above, the interpreter merged both segments into one,

whereby most of the first segment was omitted. As our analysis pertains to the translation of DMs, such cases were considered equivalent translation types, since the communicative intent of the DMs did not diverge.

5 DISCUSSION

According to the overall results, the average delivery rate of 161 TPM in the corpus TolAnSi is far from the ideal 100-120 words per minute and is considered very high, as it is at the threshold of what is currently considered still manageable, yet with potential strategic omissions by the interpreter (Setton & Dawrant, 2016). This suggests that, even though the results in Figure 2 seem less than ideal, as non-equivalent translations are predominant, they are indeed understandable and acceptable, considering the unfavourably high delivery rate. Nevertheless, since the greatest share of equivalent translation types was present in the moderate delivery rate group, this suggests that neither a very low nor a very high delivery rate is beneficial to the translation of DMs. Considering these results, the translation of DMs seems unaffected by the delivery rate, and other relevant factors need to be explored.

The analysis of the average emotive intensity of 3.12 on a scale from 1 to 5 in the corpus indicates that the speeches were rather emotionally laden than neutral. The results in Figure 3 are particularly interesting, as, without the speeches with the highest emotive intensity, the second hypothesis would have held true. Nevertheless, it must be highlighted that the group with the highest emotive intensity represents only 6.12% (and not, as it would be ideally, 20%) of the speeches. It remains, therefore, unclear, whether a higher emotive intensity affects the translation of DMs negatively, as the six speeches with the highest emotive intensity may coincidentally, or, for a different reason, have a greater share of equivalent translation types.

Irrespective of the presented research findings, it is essential to address a critical limitation. Per definition, DMs are multifunctional, meaning that they convey different intents simultaneously. The question that arises is whether their multifunctionality contradicts the process of annotating functionally (non-)equivalent pairs across languages. In our research, we strived to accommodate this limitation by allowing multiple functional annotations per

DM in both languages, and using a comprehensive functional classification allowing cross-domain mobility. Moreover, the presented DM translation type classification includes several subtypes of (close) equivalent and non-equivalent translation types, and covers the encountered translation types in the corpus. Therefore, by combining a detailed functional and translation type classification, we minimised the risk of failing to identify (non-)equivalent translation pairs.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATIONS

As the results in Figure 2 indicate, the share of equivalent DM translation types was not reduced by the rising SL delivery rate, but, conversely, was the smallest in the category with the lowest SL delivery rate and the highest in the moderate delivery rate category. Therefore, H1 was rejected.

Likewise, the emotive intensity did not seem to influence the share of equivalent translation types significantly, as the group with the highest emotive intensity (group 5) contained the most DMs with a preserved communicative intent, and it was followed by the group with the lowest emotive intensity (group 2). Consequently, H2 was also rejected.

The results gathered in the present research imply that neither the SL delivery rate nor the SL emotive intensity level influences to what degree the interpreters preserve the communicative intent of DMs. However, as emphasised in the previous section, more data are needed to provide more generalisable results. Despite both hypotheses being rejected, this research hints that other, not yet considered variables (perhaps the interpreter's experience level and the complexity of the source speech), need to be examined for their effect on the translation of DMs.

Moreover, as the DM annotation and emotive intensity assessment was provided by one annotator, it is prone to subjectivity, despite including some more objective and measurable parameters, such as speech prosody (pitch, intensity), detection of emotionally charged language, and the use of speech notes. In our future research, we therefore aim to include more human annotators, as well as automatise the process of emotive intensity assessment. Moreover, including additional languages would allow for more

generalizable findings and enable cross-cultural comparisons.

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REFERENCES

- Aijmer, K., & Simon-Vandenberg, A. M. (2003). The discourse particle *well* and its equivalents in Swedish and Dutch. *Linguistics*, *41*, 1123–1161.
- Aijmer, K. (1996). *Conversational Routines in English. Convention and Creativity*. London: Longman.
- Aijmer, K. (2007). The meaning and functions of the Swedish discourse marker *alltså* – evidence from translation corpora. *Catalan Journal of Linguistics*, *6*: 31–59.
- Andersen, G. (1998). The pragmatic marker *like* from a relevance-theoretic perspective. In A. H. Jucker & Y. Ziv (Eds.), *Discourse Markers: Description and Theory* (pp. 147–170). Amsterdam, John Benjamins.
- Bartłomiejczyk, M. (2022). Interpreting nonmainstream ideology (Euroscepticism) in the European Parliament. *Perspectives*, *30*(4), 678–694. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0907676X.2021.1939740>
- Beaton-Thome, M. (2020). Flagging the homeland: Interpreting Brexit à la Nigel Farage in the European Union. In K. Strani (ed), *Multilingualism and politics. Revisiting multilingual citizenship* (pp. 105–127). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Beňuš, Š. (2021). *Investigating spoken English: A practical guide to phonetics and phonology using Praat*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Blakemore, D., & Gallai, F. (2014). Discourse markers in free indirect style and interpreting. *Journal of Pragmatics*, *60*, 106–120.
- Cabedo, A. (2014). On the delimitation of discursive units in colloquial Spanish: Val. Es. Co application model. In *Discourse Segmentation in Romance Languages* (pp. 157–183). John Benjamins.
- Crible, L., & Degand, L. (2019). Domains and functions: A two-dimensional account of discourse markers. *Discours. Revue de linguistique, psycholinguistique et*

informatique. A journal of linguistics, psycholinguistics and computational linguistics, (24), 1–35.

- Crible, L. (2017). Towards an operational category of discourse markers: A definition and its model. In A. Sanso & C. Fedriani (Eds.), *Discourse markers, Pragmatics Markers and Modal Particles: New Perspectives* (pp. 99–124). John Benjamins.
- Dalton, D. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190416-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 21:46:49)
- Daly, C. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20191218-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 21:00:54)
- Davies, C. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190918-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 12:34:13)
- Defrancq, B., Plevoets, K., & Magnifico, C. (2015). Connective Items in Interpreting and Translation: Where Do They Come From? In J. Romero-Trillo (Ed.), *Yearbook of Corpus Linguistics and Pragmatics*, (3) (pp. 195–222).
- Degand, L., & Simon, A. C. (2009). On identifying basic discourse units in speech: theoretical and empirical issues. *Discours. Revue de linguistique, psycholinguistique et informatique. A journal of linguistics, psycholinguistics and computational linguistics*, (4).
- Degand, L., Simon, A. C., Tanguy, N., & Van Damme, T. (2014). Initiating a discourse unit in spoken French. *Discourse Segmentation Romance languages* (250), 243–273.
- Etheridge, B. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190416-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 17:57:08)
- Fedriani, C., & Sansò, A. (2017). Pragmatic Markers, Discourse Markers and Modal Particles: What do we know and where do we go from here? In A. Sanso and C. Fedriani (Eds), *Discourse markers, Pragmatics Markers and Modal Particles: New Perspectives* (pp. 1–33). John Benjamins.
- Fischer, K. (2006). Towards an understanding of the spectrum of approaches to discourse particles: introduction to the volume. In K. Fischer (Ed), *Approaches to Discourse Particles* (pp. 1–20).

- Gerver, D. (1969/2002). The Effects of Source Language Presentation Rate on the Performance of Simultaneous Conference Interpreters. In F. Pöchhacker & M. Shlesinger (Eds.), *The Interpreting Studies Reader* (pp. 52–66). London/New York: Routledge.
- Gill, N. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190313-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 17:57:50)
- Hale, S. B. (2004). *The Discourse of Court Interpreting: Discourse Practices of the Law, the Witness, and the Interpreter*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Howarth, J. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190918-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 12:24:08)
- Hu, K. (2016/2011). *Introducing Corpus-based Translation Studies*. New York: Springer.
- Hyland, K. (2005). *Metadiscourse: Exploring Interaction in Writing*. London in New York: Continuum.
- King, J. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190416-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 17:36:49)
- Korpál, P., & Jasielska, A. (2018). Investigating interpreters' empathy. *Target*, 31(1), 2–24.
- Kučiš, V., & Majhenič, S. (2018). Cultural and stress-related manifestations of political controversial language in the European Parliament from the view of interpreters. *Babel*, 64(1), 33–62.
- Lederer, M. (1981). *La Traduction Simultanée Expérience et Théorie*. Paris: Minard – Lettres Modernes.
- Magnifico, C., & Defrancq, B. (2020). Norms and gender in simultaneous interpreting: a study of connective markers. *The International Journal of Translation and Interpreting Research*, 12(1), 1–17.
- Maschler, Y., & Schiffrin, D. (2015). Discourse markers: Language, meaning, and context. In D. Tannen, H. E. Hamilton & D. Schiffrin (Eds.), *The Handbook of Discourse Analysis* (pp. 189–221), Hoboken, ZDA: John Wiley and Sons.
- Maschler, Y. (2009). *Metalanguage in Interaction. Hebrew discourse markers*.

Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.

- Mauranen, A. (2023). *Reflexively Speaking: Metadiscourse in English as a Lingua Franca*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Monti, C., Bendazzoli, C., Sandrelli, A., & Russo, M. (2005). Studying directionality in simultaneous interpreting through an Electronic Corpus: EPIC (European Parliament Interpreting Corpus). *Meta*, 50(4), np.
- Müller, S. (2005). *Discourse markers in native and non-native English discourse*. John Benjamins. Amsterdam.
- Palmer, R. (2019). Speech at the European Parliament. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/streaming/?event=20190327-0900-PLenary> (timestamp: 19:23:30)
- Redeker, G. (2006). Discourse markers as attentional cues at discourse transitions. In K. Fischer (Ed.), *Approaches to Discourse Particles* (pp. 339–358).
- Rozumko, A. (2021). Underspecification in the translation of discourse markers: A parallel corpus study of the treatment of connective functions of indeed in Polish translations. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 177, 122–134.
- Schiffrin, D. (1987). *Discourse Markers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Schiffrin, D. (2001). Discourse markers: language, meaning, and context. In D. Schiffrin, D. Tannen, and E. H. Hamilton (Eds.), *The handbook of discourse analysis* (pp. 54–75).
- Schourup, L. (1999). Discourse markers. *Lingua*, 107(3), 227–265.
- Setton, R. (2011). Corpus-based interpreting studies (CIS): Overview and prospects. In A. Kruger, K. Wallmach, & J. Munday (Eds.) *Corpus-based translation studies. Research and applications* (pp. 33–75). London: Continuum.
- Setton, R., & Dawrant, A. (2016). *Conference Interpreting: A Trainer's Guide*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: John Benjamins.
- Wang, B., & Tang, F. (2020). Corpus-based Interpreting Studies in China: Overview and Prospects. In K. Hu & K. H. Kim (Eds.) *Corpus-based Translation and Interpreting Studies in Chinese Contexts; Present and Future* (pp. 61–87). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Zwitter Vitez, A. (2018). Enota analize spontanega govora: interakcija proizvodnje, pragmatike in skladnje. *Jezik in slovstvo*, 63(2–3), 157–175.

RAZHAJANJE KOMUNIKATIVNEGA NAMENA DISKURZNIH OZNAČEVALCEV V SIMULTANO TOLMAČENEM GOVORU

Pričujoči članek preučuje razhajanje komunikativnega namena diskurznih označevalcev pri simultanem tolmačenju iz angleščine v slovenščino v Evropskem parlamentu, in sicer raziskuje vpliva hitrosti govora izhodiščnega govornika in njegove čustvene jakosti na delež enakovredno prevedenih diskurznih označevalcev, tj. takšnih, ki ohranijo enak komunikativni namen. Članek prav tako predstavlja klasifikacijo prevodov diskurznih označevalcev, namenjeno simultanemu tolmačenju angleških in slovenskih diskurznih označevalcev. Predstavljena klasifikacija izhaja iz empiričnega gradiva, ki zajema skoraj 47.000 pojavnic in upošteva vse zaznane prevodne tipe diskurznih označevalcev. Rezultati, ki temeljijo na korpusu TolAnSi, kažejo, da tako hitrost govora izhodiščnega govornika kot tudi stopnja čustvenosti ne vplivata bistveno na delež enakovredno prevedenih diskurznih označevalcev.

Keywords: diskurzni označevalci, simultano tolmačenje, hitrost govora, stopnja čustvenosti, klasifikacija tipa prevoda

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